
Tracing the Historic Foundations of 'Sarak' Identity

Anupam Jash¹

In recent years, the field of *Sarak* studies has been pre-occupied with the question of how to best define the *Sarak* religious and ethnic identity. Is it true that Saraks have always been a distinct community with their own identity. Many academics are of the opinion that different *Sarak* identities coexisted within the Hindu community up to the later part of the 19th century, and that each of these identities made an equally valid claim to be successors of ancient Jain heritage. If one looks at early Hindu socio-religious sources, it may be realized that one does not get evidences of the flexible character of *Sarak* identity as it has been claimed.

The Problem

The results of empirical investigation indicate that *'about two thirds of contemporary conflicts turn on issues of religious, ethnic, or national identity. Less than 10 percent begin as interstate conflicts'*¹. What causes conflict between religious groups and why does the preservation of religious identity lead to conflict?

What is identity?

There are numerous aspects to a person's identity. It represents a person's unique personal experience, memories, ethnicity, culture, religious orientation, gender, and occupational role, among other things. Erikson refers to identity as "some belief in the sameness and continuity of some shared world image²." Identity can be defined as one's awareness of oneself and how others perceive one's individuality. The characteristics of a person's identity depicted in Figure 1 are universal in the sense that they may be applied to a person regardless of their culture, religion, or geographic location. The characteristics depicted in Figure 1 may, at certain points in a person's life, become more prominent, such as

Associate Professor of Philosophy, Bankura Christian College

their sense of ethnicity, vocational role, or religious inclination. This may be the case based on the stage of a person's life cycle as well as the specific experiences that a person has had throughout their life. Extensive research has been conducted in the field of psychology on the topic of the connection between personal development and one's identity. Erik Erikson investigates the ways in which an adolescent's sense of identity develops as a result of their vocational and sex roles, relationships, political perspectives, and religious beliefs³.

Figure-1
The Components of Identity

Individual identity and its relationship with the group

The phrase "identity" is defined on the website www.dictionary.com as the *set of behavioral or personality characteristics by which an individual is recognizable as a member of a group*. Because of this, the individual identity of a person is inextricably tied with the identity of the group to which they belong, which might stem from any one or more of the affiliations shown in Figure 1. It would appear as well that psychologists understand the

phrase "identity per se" to mean a "subjective and persistent sense of sameness," relating primarily to the concept of group identity⁴. Some of the components in the diagram, such as nationality, ethnicity, peer grouping, social status, family, culture, and even religion, have a "groupness" component that cannot be separated from them. Nevertheless, there is no guarantee that this is how groups will develop under all contexts and circumstances. Additionally, a person may not always be aware of the "group" that they belong to or the necessity of being a part of one.

Formation of large group identity – psycho-social theories:

How does a group come to be, and what exactly does it mean to have a group identity? According to Volkan, the process of identifying with a large group (such as a religious, ethnic, or national one) begins in childhood, and the fundamental aspects of an individual's identity are intricately entwined with the identity of the large group⁵.

Volkan makes reference to Erikson's notion of "pseudo-speciation" in other places, which helps to further his comprehension of large group identification and the growth of a group's sense of superiority over other groups. In order to mention some of what Volkan had to say about the process of pseudo-speciation:

“...at the outset of human history, each human group developed a distinct sense of identity, wearing skins and feathers like armour to protect it from other groups who wore different kinds of skins and feathers. Erikson hypothesized that each group became convinced that it was the sole possessor of the true human identity. Thus each group became a pseudo-species, adopting an attitude of superiority over other groups.⁶”

The Erikson theory, on the other hand, is restricted to particular aspects of racial identity. His reasoning, however, does not consider the factors that cause "groupthink" or the underlying conditions that contribute to the development of groups. These potentially causative factors may include, but are not limited to, the following: competition over resources; power asymmetries; shared history; ethnic cleansing; heightened awareness of the perception of "the other" and dehumanization; opportunities for bonding with one's group; threat or the perception of threat from the "other" group, among other things.

Volkan elaborates on these as conditions that foster the mobilization of large groups, such as selected trauma and glories, shared grievances, and collective history. Specifically, Volkan refers to these as ‘conditions that promote the mobilization of large groups’⁷.

Religious “pseudo-speciation” and group mobilization

Could Erikson's theory of pseudo-speciation be applied to the emergence of religious subgroups under the aforementioned conditions? I would want to suggest that religious communities facing analogous pressures are especially vulnerable to adopting such mindsets. It's clear that humans, like other animals and birds, have an innate and natural tendency to congregate for many reasons. There is comfort, power, harmony, and familiarity in numbers. A sense of belonging, individuality, unity, respect, and safety are all met. When religious communities are subjected to political and economic discrimination and marginalization; when conflict is incited along ideological lines; when the threat perception is high; and when competition for finite resources is fierce, the "grouping" tendency will emerge. According to social scientists, belonging to a community helps people feel secure in themselves. It can serve as a kind of self-defence when it develops in response to aggression through group mobilization.

It's the urge to work together. Identifying with a group always leads to a focus on comparison and an awareness of one's 'self' and 'the other'. It establishes the separation and limits essential for dehumanizing the other. Because it is rooted in inviolable values and the sense of one's identity and self-esteem, a culture of pseudospeciation established on the basis of religious distinction is sometimes hard to resist or dispute. Therefore, the danger of losing one's religious identity can spark widespread and difficult-to-resolve disagreement.

Understanding the historical and religious roles in identity-based conflicts:

Marc Gopin argues that studying the patterns in religious communities requires knowledge of both socio-economics and religious psychology. He argues that cultural and religious differences obscure the importance of economic realities in comprehending the causes of conflict between minority and majority groups. Gopin, echoing the views of many of his contemporaries, argues that resistance to the status quo may "express itself in religious terms." Gopin considers the impact of religious texts, myths, metaphors, laws, attitudes, and traditions in advocating pro-social and anti-social values that contribute to conflict and offer entry points for peacemaking. He stresses the importance of religion in millions of people's personal and social lives.

“Group conflict is constituted by a series of unique human beings who evolve, for one reason or another, into a complex interaction of adversarial relationships. To understand this, we cannot suppress the roots of that human being, or group of human beings, in the historical cultures and religions from which they have

emerged. Connecting the human being to her cultural moorings will help us understand why and when she fights and when she makes peace. ”⁸

In reference to the Sarak community in Bengal and the areas that are adjacent to it in Jharkhand, we can add an essential facet to our comprehension of religious conflict. This facet is the "fear of life," which is a perception of an immediate danger on the part of a group. This leads to aggressive manifestations of conflict behavior that have the appearance of religious fundamentalism. In certain situations, playing the religion card in order to promote a political cause might effectively persuade individuals to behave in an extreme manner. The argument presented by Gopin can also be evaluated within the framework of Saraks. An examination of the dispute can shed light on the socioeconomic and political forces that lie beneath the formation of religious identity.

It might be helpful to cite Schafer's work (2004) on the dual nature of religion at this point in the discussion. Both Gopin (2002) and Appleby (2000, 2006) make mention of this dichotomy in their respective works. Schafer has a profoundly ambivalent view of religion, viewing it not only as a basis for respect but also for coexistence.

The research conducted by Schafer sheds light on a variety of topics, including religious socialization, collective ethnic identity, the emotional security derived from religious rituals and rites, and the relevance of sacred locations and shrines⁹. Schafer asserts that each of these components helps to frame a person's religious identity within the context of their community. What is particularly appalling, though, is the incapacity of religious communities to share sacred locations with other people or to interact with members of other religious communities as equal members of the human race. It is unquestionably due to the exclusivist nature of many different religious cultures that they view the introduction of the "other" into their surroundings or the encouragement of possibilities to cohabit peacefully as a significant threat.

The religious and ethnic identity of the Saraks

There is a community, that may be found in several regions of India, including West Bengal and the neighbouring regions of Jharkhand. This community is known as ‘Sarak’ community which is a religious and ethnic minority of this area. Their effect cannot be ignored, despite the fact that they do not constitute a very large population.

Someone may have the misconception that the Saraks are a community or tradition that is unique to a certain location or area within Hinduism. Because Hinduism is such a

complex religion, it is divided into numerous sects, sub-sects, and communities, each of which adheres to its own set of beliefs, rituals, and traditions. It may also be possible that the term "Saraks" refers to a certain community within Hinduism that is not well known or acknowledged by the majority of people. Their biases are more consistent with those held by Hindu religions due to the fact that they also worship Hindu deities. They belong to the Jati-varna caste system that is practiced in Hinduism. They coexist peacefully with Hindus in their community. They are a very small minority in an area that is predominately inhabited by Hindu people; as a result, they have adopted many of the same religious customs as their neighbours. In addition to this, they are ignorant regarding the various religious affiliations that they genuinely hold.

Despite the fact that the *Saraks* have just been accepted into O.B.C. categories of Hinduism, the question of the religious roots of the *Saraks* as well as the nature of their modern religious affiliations has not been answered.

Information was gathered from knowledgeable people and leaders of the *Sarak* communities and other groups to determine the extent to which Jainism currently affects the *Saraks'* way of life and culture. Although they would take part in the worship of other Hindu Gods and Goddesses, they would not honour the warrior deities *Kali* and *Viswakarma*. Do these rituals fundamentally represent a rejection of the Shakti worship and the use of force? Do these characteristics identify them as Jaina as opposed to Hindus? They do celebrate Hindu festivities with great zeal and enthusiasm.

But there is one thing that cannot be ignored. That is the gotra-name of the *Saraks*, the specific language they used in daily life, their eating habits, chosen vocations, taboos, and prejudices, are more typical of Jainism than Hinduism or other religions. For all these various reasons, it is believed that the *Saraks* belong to Jaina religion. They have been followers of some aspects of Jainism, such as vegetarianism, since ancient times, however, were isolated and separated from the main body of the Jain community in western, northern, and southern India and have been Hindu Bengalis ever since.

Etymology of the word *Sarak*

The *Saraks* are an obscure ethnic community. The word 'Sarak' derives from the Sanskrit word *Śrāvaka*, from which we get the meanings of "respect" (*śraddhā*), "awareness" (*viveka*), and "work" (*kriya*). So, a *Śrāvaka* is someone who, by chance, is a hard worker who treats others with respect. The word for a listener in Sanskrit is *Śrāvaka*. This term is used in Jainism. In Jainism, a *śrāvaka* is any lay Jain so the term *śrāvaka* has been used for the Jain

community itself (for example see *Sarak* and *Sarawagi*). *Śrāvākācāras* are the lay conduct outlined within the treaties by Śvetāmbara or Digambara mendicants. "In parallel to the prescriptive texts, Jain religious teachers have written a number of stories to illustrate vows in practice and produced a rich repertoire of characters"¹⁰.

A *śrāvaka* in Jainism is a lay Jain. He is the hearer of discourses of monastics and scholars, Jain literature. In Jainism, the Jain community is made up of four sections: monks, nuns, *śrāvakas* (laymen) and *śrāvikās* (laywomen). The term *śrāvaka* has also been used as a shorthand for the community itself. For example, the *Sarawagi* are a Jain community originating in Rajasthan, and sometimes *śrāvaka* is the origin of surnames for Jain families. The long-isolated Jain community in East India is known as the *Sarak*. The conduct of a *śrāvaka* is governed by texts called *śrāvākācāras*¹¹, the best known of which is the *Ratnakaranda śrāvākācāra* of Samantabhadra. A *śrāvaka* rises spiritually through the eleven *pratimas*¹². After the eleventh step, he becomes a monk. Jains follow six obligatory duties known as *āvashyakas*: *sāmāyika* (practising serenity), *chaturvimshati* (praising the tirthankara), *vandan* (respecting teachers and monks), *pratikramana* (introspection), *kāyotsarga* (stillness), and *pratyākhyana* (renunciation)¹³.

The History of the Saraks

The *Saraks* are an ancient community in Jharkhand and Bengal. British anthropologist Edward Tuite Dalton noted that according to the Bhumij tradition in Singhbhum district, the *Saraks* were early settlers in the region¹⁴. According to Santosh Kumar Kundu, the *Saraks* arrived from the northwestern region of India, presently in Gujarat and Uttar Pradesh. In the region between the rivers Barakar and Damodar, two democratic republics, Shikharbhum and Panchakot, flourished. Later they merged and came to be known as Shikharbhum, with the capital at Panchkot¹⁵. According to Ramesh Chandra Majumder, the Jain scholar Bhadrabahu, the second Louhacharya and the author of Kalpa Sutra may have come from the *Sarak* community¹⁶.

Jainism, whose founder Mahavira was born in the area of Vaisali and spent some of his religious career in Magadha and Champa, has its roots in eastern India. Champa is linked to *Pārsvanātha*, Mahavira's predecessor in the lineage of Tirthankaras, and Eastern India is home to the most significant Jaina locale tied to the memory of *Pārsvanātha*, the Pareshnath Hill.

Jaina literature preserves oral histories in which it is said that Mahāvira travelled to Western Bengal but was met with hostility. Although *Vanga* is frequently mentioned in the

Jaina canon¹⁷, there is no evidence to suggest that he actually travelled east of the Ganges to the land of the Pundras. *Nirgrantha* was the term under which the Jaina community was known prior to the Gupta dynasty.

Thankfully, another set of Jaina tradition demonstrates that North Bengal and a region of lower Bengal had made significant contributions to the development of the Jaina religion well before the second century B.C. Bhadrabahu, who lived at the same time as Chandragupta Maurya, is credited with writing the *Kalpasutra*¹⁸. Even if this credit is contested, there is no denying that the piece draws on ancient customs. After Bhadrabahu, the Jaina church is believed to have been divided, leading to the establishment of several separate educational institutions that maintained loose ties to one another¹⁹. According to this tradition²⁰, Godāsa, a student of Bhadrabahu, is said to have established the *Godāsa gana*, a school that eventually grew to include four *sākhās*, three of which are known as the Tamraliptika, Kotivarshiya, and Pundravardhaniya.

The first is located in southern Bengal, while the other two are in northern Bengal and are both well-known tourist destinations. The *Kalpasutra* tradition was well established by the end of the first century B.C. and the first century A.D.²¹, as evidenced by the huge number of school names found in inscriptions from that time periods. A Jaina monk from Radha area, is said to have requested the construction of a Jaina image in a Mathura inscription from the second century A.D.

There are references to the installation of statues of Jaina *tirthankara* Lord *Pārsvanātha* and other *tirthankaras* in several Gupta-era inscriptions, but none of these are from Bengal. A copper-plate from the city of Pāharpur dating back to the year 159 (478-79 A.D.) is the lone exception. It provides evidence that a Jaina *vihara* existed in the *Vata-Gohala* area, "which was presided over by the disciples and the disciples of disciples of the *Nirgrantha* acharya Guhanandin belonging to the *Pancha-stupa* section of Benares." The Great Temple and Monastery, recently discovered in Paharpur, stood on the site of the *vihara*, which was thus founded in the 4th century A.D., if not earlier still.

Hiuen Tsang seems to imply that the *Nirgranthas* were the pre-eminent religious group over all of Bengal in the seventh century. This includes both northern and southern Bengal as well as eastern Bengal. The pilgrim says, "the Digambara *Nirgranthas* were very numerous" in reference to the heretics at Pundravardhana and Samatata.

The *Nirgranthas*, on the other hand, appear to have entirely vanished from Bengal in the succeeding century, with no mention of them in the countless inscriptions of the Palas and Senas. Only immigrants from Western India re-established the old faith in its new form, now

known as Jainism, in various districts of North Bengal during the Muhammadan period." The naked *Nirgrantha* ascetics had most likely merged in religious communities such as the *Avadhutas*, which had become well established in Bengal by the end of the Pala period.²²"

The descendants of the Jaina lay people who lived in this region, notably in the eastern part of India, are known as *Saraks*. They are the direct disciples of the *Nirgranthas* or the Jaina Monks. They inhabited this region between the sixth century B.C. and the twelfth century AD. They established their own community predominately in the states of Bengal, Bihar, Jharkhand, and Orissa where they lived.

The Jaina *Sarak* community lost contact with mainstream of the Jaina community in the rest of India after its conquest by Ikhtiyar Uddin Muhammad bin Bakhtiyar Khilji.

Now a days the *Sarak* peoples are concentrated in Purulia, Bankura and Burdwan district of West Bengal and Ranchi, Dumka and Giridih districts and Singhbhum region of Jharkhand. The *Saraks* belonging to most of Jharkhand and West Bengal are Bengali speakers while those living in historical Singhbhum region speak Hindi and Singhbhumi Odia. Educated *Saraks* speak fluent English.

In 2009, more than 165 *Sarak* Jains living in parts of West Bengal, Jharkhand and Bihar visited the ancient Jain pilgrimage centre of Shravanabelagola. A special function to welcome the *Sarak* Jains was organised at Shravanabelagola²³.

In the official statistics, they are not taken into account as a distinct population group. The governments of India and West Bengal both have classified some of the *Saraks* under Other Backward Classes since 1994 but many of them have been in the General category from the beginning itself²⁴.

Religion-Ethnic Identity: The Jain *Sarak* community is primarily Jain, and their religious practices follow both the Svetambara and the Digambara sect. They have established several Jain temples in the Bengal and Jharkhand region in past, and their community members actively participate in religious events and ceremonies. They are also proud of their ethnic identity and maintain their unique cultural practices and traditions.

The characteristics of the *Sarak* communities are as follows:

1. The *Saraks* adhere to a spiritual lifestyle.
2. They probably don't drink alcohol, eat fish or meat of any type, and follow a strict vegetarian diet, so that's a good place to start.
3. You won't find any fur, wood, silk, or leather among their wardrobe selections.

4. They have a naturally pristine demeanour, as evidenced by their frequent showers and spotless attire.
5. They avoid immoral behaviour like stealing, decoying, robbing, etc., because of their commitment to nonviolence.
6. They avoid any line of work that can involve them in or promote violence.
7. Many *Saraks* from Talajuri and Senera village also claimed to be related to the Vaishyas. They gave the following explanations:
8. They dress plainly and accessorize with commonplace items.
9. They do not invest heavily in group meals or consuming alcohol together.
10. They work in agriculture and are known for their extreme frugality.
11. Women in particular are heavily interested in investing in money-landing businesses.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we may say that, the Jain *Sarak* community has made a significant contribution to the socio-economic development of West Bengal and adjacent areas of Jharkhand. They have established themselves as successful traders and have contributed to the growth of the local economy. Their strong religious and ethnic identity has helped them maintain their unique cultural practices and traditions.

[Acknowledgement: The author is thankful to Indian Council of Social Science Research (ICSSR) for awarding the Major Project Grant (F. No.02/194/2022-23/ICSSR/RP/MJ/ GEN Dated: 29-03-2023)]

References

1. R. Scott Appleby, (2000) *Ambivalence of the Sacred* (New York: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers, Inc.), p.17
2. E.H. Erikson, (1970) “*Reflections on the Dissent of Contemporary Youth*”, International Journal of Psychoanalysis, 51, p.18
3. E.H. Erikson, (1968) *Identity: Youth and Crisis* (New York: Norton Press)
4. Vamik Volkan, (2006) *Killing in the Name of Identity* (Virginia: Pitchstone Publishing), p.14
5. Vamik Volkan, (2005) “*Large Group Identity, Large Group Regression and Massive Violence*”, International Newsletter of the Group-Analytic Society, December 30, 2005, p. 11.
6. Vamik Volkan, (2006) *Killing in the Name of Identity* (Virginia: Pitchstone Publishing, p.15
7. Vamik Volkan, (1997), *Blood Lines: From Ethnic Pride to Ethnic Terrorism* (Colorado: Westview Press, pp.50-80
8. Marc Gopin, (2002), *Between Eden and Armageddon* (New York: Oxford University Press, pp.5-6
9. Schafer, H., (2004) “*The Janus Face of Religion: On the Religious Factor in New Wars*”, NUMEN, 51, (4).
10. Balbir, Nalini. "Article: Vows". www.jainpedia.org. Retrieved 22 May 2019.
11. Shastri, Hiralal Jain (1988), *Shravakachar Sangrah*, Five Volumes, Jain Sanskruti Samrakshak Sangh Solapur,
12. Williams R. (2000) *Jaina yoga: a survey of the mediaeval śrāvakācāras*, New Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass
13. Jaini P. S. (1998), *The Jaina Path of Purification*. New Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, pp. 190.
14. Ghosh, Binay (2010) [1957]. *Pashchimbanger Samskriti* [The Culture of West Bengal] (in Bengali). Vol. 1 (2nd ed.). Kolkata: Prakash Bhawan. pp. 447–449.
15. Kundu, Santosh Kumar (2008). *Bangali Hindu Jati Parichay* [An Introduction of Bengali Hindu Castes] (in Bengali). Kolkata: Presidency Library. pp. 273–275.
16. Majumdar R. C. ed. (1943). *The History of Bengal*, Vol.1 . Dacca: The University of Dacca. p.410.
17. Levi, S. (1929) *Pre-Aryam and Pre-ravidian in India* (Eng. translation by P. C. Bagchi), Calcutta: The University of Calcutta. pp. 73 ff.
18. Winternitz, M. (2015) *A History of Indian Literature*, Vol. II. p. 462 ; the Kalpasutra is the 8th section of the Aydradasao
19. Winternitz, M. (2015) *A History of Indian Literature*, Vol. II. p. 462 ; the Kalpasutra is the 8th section of the Aydradasao
20. *Jaina Sutras* (translation of Jacobi), SBE. xxii, p. 288
21. Guerinot, *Epigraphic Jaina*, pp. 36 ff, 71 ff.

22. Banerji, R. D, (2021) *Palas of Bengal*, by R. D, Banerji (MASB. Vol. V). New Delhi:Gyan Publishing, p.72
23. News Updates. www.Jainheritagecentres.com. 2 September 2009. Archived from the original on 23 December 2015.
24. “*Government of West Bengal: List of Other Backward Classes*”. Govt. of West Bengal. Retrieved 23 December 2011.